

Preparation and Characterisation of Dithiocarbamate Complexes of Tri-n-butyltin(IV)

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Tri-n-butyltin(IV) dithiocarbamate complexes of the type $R_3SnS_2CNR'R''$ and R_3SnS_2CNR''' , where $R = n\text{-butyl}$; $R' = \text{Me, Et, } i\text{-Pr}$; $R'' = \text{benzyl}$; $R''' = \text{morpholine, 4,6-dimethylmorpholine, 4-methylpiperazine or 4-methylpiperidine}$, have been prepared by the reaction of tri-n-butyltin chloride with the respective sodium salt of dithiocarbamic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dry acetone. The ir and 1H nmr spectral studies of these dithiocarbamate complexes indicate unidentate behaviour of dithiocarbamate moiety with the central tin metal atom having a coordination number four.

THE first report of clearly defined phenyltin tridithiocarbamate complexes came from Kupchik and Calabretta¹ in 1965. An extension of this work was reported by Bonati and Ugo^{2,3}. Besides the synthesis of organotin(IV)-*N,N*-dithiocarbamates, several physicochemical and spectroscopic techniques, e.g. infrared^{4,11}, nmr^{6,11}, Mössbauer¹⁰⁻¹⁶ and X-ray diffraction have been used to investigate the structure of organotin-dithiocarbamates, i.e. to identify the bonding behaviour of the dithiocarbamate moiety which may be unidentate, bidentate or anisobidentate and to establish the coordination number of the central metal atom and stereochemistry of the molecule. The bidentate behaviour of the dithiocarbamate moiety in $R_3Sn(IV)$ and $RSn(IV)$ *N,N*-disubstituted-dithiocarbamates^{2,4,16-18} is well established. While Bonati *et al.* have suggested that in the corresponding $R_3Sn(IV)$ compounds no concrete evidence is found for or against the chelation of dithiocarbamate moiety, Srivastava *et al.*^{6,19} and Sharma *et al.*¹¹ have reported monodentate character for the $R_3Sn(IV)$ $S_2CNR'_2$ complexes.

The present communication reports the synthesis and characterisation of some new tri-organotin-dithiocarbamates of the type $R_3SnS_2CNR'R''$ and R_3SnS_2CNR''' , where $R = n\text{-butyl}$; $R' = \text{Me, Et, } i\text{-Pr}$; $R'' = \text{benzyl}$; $R''' = \text{morpholine, 2,6-dimethylmorpholine, 4-methylpiperazine or 4-methylpiperidine}$. These complexes have been characterised on the basis of elemental analysis and ir and 1H nmr spectral data.

Experimental

Sodium salt of dithiocarbamic acid: Sodium salt of dithiocarbamic acids (benzyl methyl, benzyl

ethyl, benzyl isopropyl, morpholine, 2,6-dimethylmorpholine, *N*-methylpiperazine or 4-methylpiperidine) were prepared in good yields by the reaction of the appropriate secondary amine, carbon disulphide and sodium hydroxide as described in the literature^{20,21}.

Tributyltin chloride: It was prepared by the chlorination of hexabutyl distannane²².

Tri-n-butyltin-dithiocarbamates: To a solution of tri-n-butyltin chloride (3.25 g, 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (30 ml) was added dropwise, with constant stirring, a solution of sodium salt of methyl, benzyl dithiocarbamic acid (2.19 g, 0.01 mol) in dry acetone (25 ml). The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 h and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to leave behind a yellow coloured viscous liquid which upon subsequent distillation under vacuum gave a colourless viscous liquid in 80% yields. The formation of new triorganotin(IV) dithiocarbamates may be represented by the following equation:

The other tri-n-butyltin-dithiocarbamates were prepared by similar procedure. Quantitative estimation of carbon and hydrogen was done by using microanalytical apparatus, nitrogen by Kjeldahl method, and tin and sulphur estimated gravimetrically as SnO_2 and barium sulphate, respectively. Analytical data are given in Table I.

Physicochemical measurements: Infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 621 grating spectrometer as thin films in the region 4000–250 cm^{-1} . 1H nmr spectra were recorded at 28° and

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF TRI-*n*-BUTYLTIN(IV)

Compd.*	B.p., °C (Pressure, mm)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				
		C	H	N	S	Sn
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(OH) ₂ (CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	129.30 (0.5)	50.49 (51.88)	7.44 (7.61)	3.05 (2.88)	12.86 (13.17)	23.98 (21.43)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(<i>n</i> -C ₄ H ₉)(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	134.5 (1.0)	51.95 (52.53)	7.52 (7.80)	2.69 (2.80)	12.27 (12.80)	24.37 (23.75)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(<i>i</i> -C ₄ H ₉)(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	138.9 (0.5)	54.21 (53.72)	8.30 (7.98)	2.61 (2.72)	13.01 (12.45)	23.92 (23.10)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(C ₄ H ₉ O)	122.3 (1.5)	44.20 (45.16)	7.04 (7.74)	2.91 (3.09)	14.48 (14.16)	27.06 (26.27)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ (CHCH ₃) ₂ O	140.1 (0.2)	47.01 (47.53)	7.95 (8.13)	3.11 (2.92)	13.01 (13.34)	24.27 (24.74)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ NCH ₃	110.1 (0.2)	45.97 (46.48)	8.42 (8.18)	6.46 (6.03)	14.03 (13.77)	24.92 (25.54)
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ CHCH ₃	145.6 (1.0)	49.57 (49.17)	8.03 (8.41)	3.19 (3.02)	13.39 (13.90)	24.95 (25.60)

* All compds. liquid.

at sweep width of 500 Hz with a Varian A-60 spectrometer. The magnetic field sweep was calibrated with a standard sample of chloroform and tetramethylsilane (1%) in deuterated chloroform.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes were colourless viscous liquids, soluble in chloroform, benzene, acetone, dichloromethane, carbon tetrachloride and were quite stable at room temperature in dry atmosphere.

The dithiocarbamate complexes of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) (Table 2) show two bands ~1490 and

in the region $330 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to Sn—S stretching mode²⁶.

¹H nmr spectra: The room temperature nmr spectra of various dithiocarbamate complexes of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV) (Table 3), show two types of signals, i.e. due to Sn-butyl group and NR₂ protons. The appearance of a single peak at $\tau \sim 6.5$ for methyl protons in the spectra of *N*-methyl-*N*-benzyl-dithiocarbamate of tri-*n*-butyltin and similarly the appearance of one quartet at $\tau \sim 5.95$ due to N—CH₂ protons and one triplet at $\tau \sim 8.6$ due to CH₃ protons of the ethyl group in the spectra of *N*-ethyl-*N*-benzyl-dithiocarbamate of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV), indicate that the N-bonded R groups are equivalent in these complexes. In the case of *N*-isopropyl-*N*-benzyl-dithiocarbamate, a doublet is observed at $\tau 8.8$ due to CH₃ protons of the isopropyl group and a clear heptet at $\tau 4.14$ due to the N-bonded CH protons of the isopropyl group. The benzyl group in the *N*-methyl-*N*-benzyl, *N*-ethyl-*N*-benzyl, *N*-isopropyl-*N*-benzyl (dtc) complexes of tri-*n*-butyltin is well characterised by the presence of a singlet at $\tau \sim 4.5$ due to N—CH₂ protons and singlet at $\tau 2.3$ due to the phenyl protons of the benzyl group²⁷. A doublet at $\tau \sim 4.5$ (due to N—CH₂ protons), a triplet at $\tau 6.74$ (due to C—CH₂ protons) and a multiplet at $\tau 8.2$ (due to CH protons) with a doublet at $\tau 9.0$ (due to C—CH₃ protons) characterise the heterocyclic 4-methylpiperidine group in 4-methylpiperidine (dtc) complex of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV). The *N*-methylpiperazine group in tri-*n*-butyltin-*N*-methylpiperazine (dtc) complex is characterised by the presence of two types of proton resonance signals: one triplet at $\tau 5.48$ due to the CH₂ protons bonded to nitrogen of the (dtc) moiety and triplet at $\tau 7.32$ due to the CH₂ protons bonded to the other nitrogen bonded to CH₃ group²⁸. The protons of this CH₃ group show a singlet at $\tau 7.5$. In case of tri-*n*-butyltin-morpholine (dtc) two types of group proton signals due to CH₂ protons of the morpholine are obtained, i.e. at $\tau 5.7$ due to N—CH₂ protons and at $\tau 6.2$ due to O—CH₂ protons²⁸. In the 2,6-dimethylmorpholinedithiocarbamate of tri-*n*-butyltin(IV), two types of protons

TABLE 2—RELEVANT IR BANDS OF DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF TRI-*n*-BUTYLTIN(IV)

Compd.	(C=N)	(C=S) (Sn—S)	
	cm ⁻¹	cm ⁻¹	cm ⁻¹
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(OH) ₂ (CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	1495m 1480m	1000m 985s	385n
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(C ₄ H ₉)(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	1490s 1475s	1025m 995s	380m
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(<i>i</i> -C ₄ H ₉)(CH ₃ C ₆ H ₅)	1495s 1465s	1030m 1000m	370m
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(C ₄ H ₉ O)	1465b	1005s 985m	380m
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(OH) ₂ (CHCH ₃) ₂ O	1460s 1450m	990s 960s	380m
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ NCH ₃	1460vs 1450m	1020s 995vs	380m
(<i>n</i> -Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₃) ₂ CHCH ₃	1480-450b	1030m 1000m	320m

b=broad m=medium, s=strong, vs=very strong w=weak.

~1000 cm⁻¹, assigned to the C=N and (C=S) vibrations, respectively. The splitting of the band ~1000 cm⁻¹ with a separation value >20 cm⁻¹ indicates the unidentate nature of the dithiocarbamate moiety in these samples^{28, 29, 30, 31, 32, 33-35}. In the far-infrared region of the spectra, intense bands at 500-520 cm⁻¹ and ~600 cm⁻¹ are assigned to symmetric and asymmetric Sn—C stretching modes. The presence of two Sn—C bands indicates the non-linearity of the C—Sn—C moiety. A strong band

TABLE 3—¹H NMR SPECTRAL DATA* OF DITHIOCARBAMATO COMPLEXES OF TRI-n-BUTYL TIN(IV)

Compd.	Proton signals due to Sn-R protons τ (μm)	Proton signals due to NR ₂ protons τ (ppm)			
		CH ₂	CH ₂	CH	O, H ₂
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₂) ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅)	7.88 - 9.10 (m)	6.5 (s)	4.50 (s)	—	2.24 (s)
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅) ₂ CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅)	7.8 - 9.15 (m)	8.6 (t)	5.95 (q)	—	2.28 (s)
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(i-C ₄ H ₇)(CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅)	7.88 - 9.05 (m)	8.8 (d)	4.55 (s)	—	—
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(C ₂ H ₅ O)	7.80 - 9.08 (m)	—	4.58 (s)	4.14 (m)	2.35 (s)
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ ON(CH ₂) ₂ (OCHCH ₃) ₂ O	7.70 - 9.05 (m)	8.7 (d)	6.2	—	—
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ ON(CH ₂) ₂ NOH ₂	7.70 - 9.05 (m)	8.7 (d)	5.7	6.0	—
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ ON(CH ₂) ₂ NOH ₂	7.88 - 9.10 (m)	7.5 (s)	6.92	—	—
(n-Bu) ₃ SnS ₂ CN(CH ₂) ₂ CHCH ₃	7.68 - 9.06 (m)	9.00 (d)	4.35	—	—
			7.32 (t)	—	—
			5.48 (t)	—	—
			6.7	8.2 (m)	—
			4.5	—	—

* Spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ solution.

d = doublet, m = multiplet, t = triplet, s = singlet, q = quartet.

signals are observed due to N-bonded CH₂ protons, i.e. at τ 4.35 and 6.92. The other characteristic signals of the 2,6-dimethylmorpholine group are a complex multiplet at τ 6.0 due to CH protons and doublet at τ ~ 8.70 due to CH₂ protons. These two types of proton signals probably arise due to the following structure,

which shows the unidentate behaviour of the dithiocarbamate moiety. The n-butyl group bonded to the metal in various dthc complexes of tri-n-butyltin(IV) is well characterised by the presence of a multiplet in the region τ 7.7 - 9.7.

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